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Development of Yellow Mosaic Virus Resistant Genotypes in Urdbean TNAU blackgram VBN 6: A high yielding blackgram variety with resistant to Mungbean Yellow Mosaic Virus

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Abstract

The Blackgram culture VBG04-014 is a cross derivative of Vamban 1 x *Vigna mungo* var. *silvestris* 1 released as variety TNAU Blackgram VBN(Bg)6, it is maturing in 65-70 days and suited for cultivation under both rainfed and irrigated conditions. It has an average yield potential of 871 Kg per hectare. This culture is resistant to Yellow Mosaic Virus, Leaf Curl Virus and less damage of pod borer. It possesses desirable characters like high protein content (21.1%). Grains are medium sized with black in colour. It is recommended for cultivation in Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: VBG04-014; Blackgram; Yellow Mosaic Virus; Rainfed; Irrigated

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